

INTERFACIAL BEHAVIORS OF CAST-IN HARDFACING COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Cast-in hardfacing material is one of the composite materials with metal matrix reinforced by tungsten carbide particulates. In this paper, composite with steel and iron base metals were experimented in the same conditions. The binder phase metal was chromium ferroalloy. The matrix-particulate interfaces were formed as shells around the tungsten carbide particulates. The volume percentage of tungsten carbide particulates in iron and steel base composites was 48.2-56.9 and 32-52.3% respectively. 3 body abrasive wear test was carried out in a rotary tester. The resistance of wear of iron and steel base composite was 3.57-8.31 and 2.61-5.42 respectively. Results showed that the volume percentage of tungsten carbide and resistance of wear of iron base metal composite were higher than that of steel base metal composite. Evidently, interfacial behaviors was promoted when the composite materials cast-in by lower melting point metals.

Keywords: metallic matrix, particulate composite, interface, wear.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cast-in hardface composite material is one of the composite materials with metal matrix reinforced by tungsten carbide particulates. It distinguishes from composite materials reinforced by fibers. As well known, the latter has been more plentifully investigated than the former. There are many fabrication technologies for composite materials reinforced by fibers and also many studies, theoretical descriptions and calculations about the macro or micro structures. Firstly, the adherent behavior of the fiber and matrix, i.e., the fiber-matrix interface performance is one of the important factors of composite materials (1). Although composite material reinforced by fiber or particulate has their own specialities, the theory for estimation of their adherent behaviors is almost the same. Secondly, the requirements of the performance of composite materials are different due to the materials are not under the likely service conditions. It is suitable to evaluate the performance of the composite materials according to their service conditions. Some papers(2,3) investigated the performances of the particulate composite. This paper investigated the foregoing problems and tried to study interfacial behaviors of particulate composite by the method of wear abrasion test. During the test process, the abrasives translate and turn on the matrix, particulates and their interfaces under pressure. In fact, silica abrasives cut and plough on materials. The interface strength tends to support the particulates to prevent particulates spalling from the surface of material. The test process employed here has been used to test steel base and iron base composite materials reinforced by tungsten carbide particulates. Tungsten carbide particulates and their supporter, interfacial reaction products contributed to wear resistance effectively.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1. Materials and fabrication

Specimens were cast-in by vacuum moulding process. Tungsten carbide particulates and Cr alloy particles were mixed in different grain size and compacted on the surface of mould cavity. Cast iron or steel liquid was poured into the mould cavity. Consequently, the cast-in hardfacing composite materials were finished.

Table 1. Grain size and volume ratio of particulates

Specimens No.		Volume ratio of particulates	
Substrates			
Steel	Cast iron		
S1	C1	80 % WC (80 / 100 mesh)	20 % Cr ferroalloy
S2	C2	80 % WC (100 / 120 mesh)	20 % Cr ferroalloy
S3	C3	80 % WC (120 / 140 mesh)	20 % Cr ferroalloy
S4	C4	80 % WC (140 / 200 mesh)	20 % Cr ferroalloy

2.2. Three-body abrasion test

Composites have their own bonding behaviors when they are made of different materials. As well known, the test and calculating method of composite materials reinforced by particulates are few. Here three-body abrasion test contributed to this effect. Three-body abrasion test was carried out by a rebuilt abrasion wear tester. Specimens rotated on a circular plate with linear speed of 16.4 M/min.. The silica sand (70 / 140 mesh, HV 1200) was put on the plate. Specimens were tested under normal pressure of 50 KPa. Reference specimen was low carbon steel (0.20% C, normalized). During testing, silica sand translated or turned between the specimen and circular plate. Ploughing and cutting effects occurred due to the relative motion of the angular silica sands and specimens. The weight of specimens reduced due to wear abrasion. And the relative wear resistance

$W = \text{Weight loss of reference specimen} / \text{weight loss of specimen tested}$

3. RESULTS

3.1. Volume percentages of particulates

The volume percentages of tungsten carbide particulates retained in cast iron and steel base composite materials are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Volume % of WC particulates in cast iron (C) and steel (S) composites

Figure 1 illustrates the volume percentage of WC particulates in cast iron base composite is higher than that in steel base composite with the same grain size of WC particulates.

3.2. Compositions of interfacial products

Photographs of the interfacial products were examined by SEM. Photograph 1 and 2 illustrate the morphologies of the interfacial products. Diffusion shells, seem to be dissolved WC whiskers, occurred around the particulates.

The new complex reaction products, polygon carbides exist outside the shells. The local composition of the carbides were examined by X-ray energy dispersive analysis JSM-35C. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Compositions of Complex carbides

Specimen No.	Chemical compositions %				
	W	Cr	Fe	Si	Mn
Iron base C	10.54	11.64	72.36	4.31	1.01
Steel base S	67.09	2.24	30.24		0.43

It illustrates that the tungsten content of complex carbides of iron base composite is much lower than that of steel base composite.

3.3. Wear resistance

The relative wear resistances examined by three-body wear abrasion test are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The wear resistances of iron and steel base composites

Figure 2 shows that the relative wear resistance of iron base composite C1-C4 is higher than that of steel base composite S1-S4 respectively.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. The composite materials existed in thermal field when liquid iron or steel was poured into cavity of mold, the iron or steel infiltrated into the interspaces of WC particulates. The WC particulates were dissolved around

their surfaces and reacted with the infiltrated metal due to mutual component diffusion, although the melting point of tungsten carbide is higher than the temperature of infiltrated metals.

The volume percentage of tungsten carbide particulates of iron base composite is higher than that of steel base composite containing the same grain size of WC particulates, because the WC particulates have their respective dissolubilities in different thermal fields.

4.2. During three-body wear abrasion test, the higher the WC volume percentage the material takes, the higher the wear resistance the material gets. No matter what type of wear abrasion happens, the tungsten carbide particulates exist as antiwear frames. Because not only the hardness of WC particulate is much higher than that of silica abrasives ($H_m / H_a = 2.3$) (4), but also the area of WC particulates much more exist on the abraded surface.

4.3. The binder alloy and base metal must be adequately selected so that matrix and reaction products form stronger interface supporting tungsten carbide particulates and reduce its dissolution. In this paper, the hardness of complex carbide was examined as 1440 HV. By virtue of three-body wear test, interfacial behavior exhibited as a stronger support of tungsten carbide particulates and contributed effectively to wear resistance.

5. CONCLUSIONS

5.1. Volume percentage of tungsten carbide particulates of iron base composite is higher than that of steel base composite.

5.2. Tungsten carbide particulates contribute to wear resistance effectively.

5.3. Interfacial reaction products strongly support the tungsten carbide particulates to prevent particulates spalling.

5.4. Relative wear resistance of iron base composite is higher than that of steel base composite.

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Photograph 1. Morphology of composite S1

Photograph 2. Morphology of composite C1